

Pythagoras' Theorem and Geometric Circle Not Square Areas

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Pythagoras' theorem, $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$ is often viewed geometrically as the sum of the area of a square x^2 and another square area y^2 yielding a square area r^2 , where r is the hypotenuse of a right angle triangle. We argue, however, that this equation, when multiplied by 3.14 represents the sum of the areas of circles and so there is no a priori reason to necessarily focus on the area of squares, even though that it one geometrical interpretation. The circle area geometrical interpretation is just as good, and leads to the derivation of Pythagoras' theorem, we argue.

Given that $3.14 r^2$ is the area of a circle with radius r , we argue that if one has r lying on the x axis of a usual 2-space co-ordinate system, one may write $(r,0)$ and define $(r,0) \cdot (r,0) = r^2$ in order to obtain the circle area. It is possible to rotate r to create a right angle triangle with (x,y) representing the lengths of the two non-hypotenuse sides. If one follows the rule for multiplying pairs, then $(x,y) \cdot (x,y) = x^2 + y^2$, but this is not necessarily equal to r^2 .

To show that it is, one may note that one may create a 2x2 matrix R such that R acting on $(r,0) = (x,y)$. If one then takes $(r,0) R^{\text{transpose}} R (r,0)$ (as a column) then $R^{\text{transpose}} R = 1$ will yield the circle area (when multiplied by 3.14, so $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$ based on a geometrical interpretation of r^2 , the hypotenuse squared as really the area of a circle (when multiplied by 3.14.).

Given the large amount of attention given to Pythagoras' theorem it is possible that the above ideas or similar ones have already been discussed in the literature.

Pythagoras' Theorem and Square Areas

Traditionally, it seems that Pythagoras' theorem:

$$x^2 + y^2 = r^2 \quad ((1))$$

Is interpreted geometrically as the area of a square of side x plus the area of a square of side y equalling the area of a square of side r , which is the hypotenuse. We argue that one may multiply this equation by 3.14 to obtain the sum of areas of circles. The circle area interpretation is just as legitimate as the square one. We further suggest that one may use the circle interpretation to derive ((1)).

Consider the area of a circle given by: $\text{circle area} = 3.14 r^2$ ((2))

If r lies along x in some 2-axis co-ordinate system one may write $(r,0) \cdot (r,0) = r^2 + 0^2$. For r lying along the y axis, one may write $(0,r) \cdot (0,r) = 0^2 + r^2$. Thus, we define a dot product. If one rotates r to create a right angle triangle, then one may write the ordered pair (x,y) describing the two side lengths with r still being a radius and the length of the hypotenuse. Given the dot product definition:

$$(x,y) \cdot (x,y) = x^2 + y^2 \quad ((3))$$

One may, however, write: $(x,y) = R (r,0)$ where R is a matrix. Then:

$$(x,y) \cdot (x,y) = (r,0) R^{\text{transpose}} R (r,0) \text{ (the latter is a column vector)}$$

If $R^{\text{transpose}} R =$ the identity matrix, then one has: $xx+yy= rr$.

In order to explicitly calculate R, one may start with:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x/r & M \\ y/r & N \end{pmatrix} \quad ((4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{To have } R^{\text{transpose}} R = \text{identity: } & \begin{pmatrix} x/r & y/r \\ M & N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x/r & M \\ y/r & N \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((5)) \\ & \begin{pmatrix} x/r & y/r \\ M & N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x/r & M \\ y/r & N \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{So } xx/rr + yy/rr = 1, \quad Mx/r + Ny/r=0 \quad \text{and } MM + NN=1$$

$$\text{A solution is: } M=-y/r \quad N=x/r \quad ((6))$$

By using the geometric interpretation of areas of circles for the Pythagoras' theorem, one may derive the theorem.

Square Area Interpretation

Even though the Pythagoras' theorem was derived above using the notion of circle areas, $xx+yy=rr$ applies equally well to square areas. How may one make the two geometric interpretations compatible?

If a square transcribed in a circle with the hypotenuse (at a 45 degree angle) representing a diameter has an area ratio to the area of the circle which is a constant, then a sum of areas of squares equals the sum of areas of circles. Using trigonometry, the square side is $r \sin(45) = r/\sqrt{2}$. Thus, the square area is $rr/2$ which when divided by the area of the circle, $3.14 rr$, is a constant. Thus, the square area geometry follows from the circle area geometry.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that even though traditionally Pythagoras' theorem is viewed geometrically as the sum of areas of squares, one may equally well consider it to represent the sum of areas of circles by multiplying by 3.14. We show that the circle view allows one to derive the relation and that one may transcribe a square within a circle such that the square area to circle area is the same constant for any circle. Thus, the area of circles approach may also yield the sum of areas of squares as an equivalent solution. The derivation of Pythagoras' theorem, however, is easily obtained using the circle area view point.

